

STUDYING THE SYSTEM OF ATTITUDE TO THE CHOICE OF A PROFESSION

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Abstract. *The school is designed to ensure readiness to choose a profession, develop professional interests and inclinations of the individual. At the final stage of schooling, high school students should be ready to choose a profession and continue to receive education.*

The article deals with the task of getting schoolchildren of different ages and gender interested in the profession, developing labor skills, using their inner potential (self-expression).

Keywords: *choice, profession, develop, interest, inclination, readiness, interest, skills, inner potential, self-expression.*

Currently, special attention is paid to the purposeful organization and implementation of the educational process, the development of management methods and tools, and attitudes towards choosing a profession. This clearly shows that it is important to keep up with these updates and improve the professional competence of the staff.

In the process of learning, students learn the basics of science, form a certain imagination, choose a profession to their liking. The origin of their inclinations, passions, aspirations, desires, motives, virtues, especially their interests, motives, needs in the profession is inextricably linked with the personal problem of psychology. Studying personality psychology means helping students choose a profession. One of the important tasks of personality psychology is to orient each of the students to a reasonable profession, taking into account their individual typological characteristics, age and gender.

The choice of a profession by young people mainly begins in the senior grade, therefore, teachers and psychologists have an important task to interest schoolchildren of different ages and gender in the profession, develop work skills, and use their inner potential (self-expression). Psychologists, in addition, should develop methods, techniques, technologies, criteria and components of intelligence to determine the intelligence, abilities and level of suitability of students for a particular profession, as well as conduct research in this area. It should be emphasized that psychological science has not yet fully developed guidelines and recommendations, excellent manuals, professionograms of most professions that help students choose a profession. But practical and theoretical materials on the psychology of personality have been created in sufficient quantity. By clarifying the issues of personality psychology, i.e., determining a person's cognitive abilities, intelligence, quick wits, individual typological features, mental states, one can give a clear idea of what he is capable of and what profession he is suitable for.

A number of scientists of world psychology covered the methodological foundations of behavior and interpersonal relationships. Foreign psychologists (R. Plomin and H. Hermans) showed that the perfect formation of a person is determined by the influence of 3 main factors. This:

1. The biological possibility that exists in man - refers to the influence of the type of temperament on the processes of human interaction.

2. Makes the strategy of the process subjective, that is, the psychological capabilities of a person; he personally chooses the interaction and complements and enhances them in social life.

3. The process of interpersonal relations affects the socio-cultural, spiritual and ethical formation of relations and personality. The sociocultural environment ensures the formation of personality as the main mechanism of interpersonal relations.

Scientists drew attention to the fact that all three factors are interconnected and create a perfect human development. Career guidance for students is carried out by the class teacher, school psychologist, career counselor and teachers of natural sciences. Their main tasks:

1. Formation of a positive attitude towards work.
2. Be able to understand the structure of professional activity.
3. Knowledge of personal characteristics required by the profession.
4. The ability to objectively assess your capabilities and abilities

The German teacher R. Steiner (1861-1925) is the founder of Waldorf pedagogy, which, unlike traditional education, focuses on the intellectual development of the child. According to the concept of the famous American pragmatist and educator John Dewey (1859-1952), that the development of the child's internal forces should be based on his random interests and inclinations, education should be based on the child's play and work activities, in which each of his actions becomes an instrument of thinking [1].

L.S. Vygotsky, A.N. Leontiev, D.B. Elkonin are the founders of the principle of the activity approach to child psychology. In his opinion, the mental development of the child has a social nature and is improved through the products of material and spiritual culture. Motives occupy a leading place in mental development. Accordingly, it is very important to find motivation in children [2].

Psychologists, methodologists, employees of the diagnostic center, together with the general public, should widely promote knowledge about the profession, develop methodological recommendations and methods for choosing a profession, expand official career guidance departments, increase the volume of professionograms, professionographs, and psychograms. .

The goal of career guidance is not to force the child to consciously choose a profession, but to form objective ideas about the types and characteristics of professions , including:

- the formation in children of a positive attitude towards the world of professions and work; to form a desire to constantly and consistently engage in age-appropriate work at the level of their capabilities.
- the main direction of career orientation is vocational education, which includes the desire to acquire the virtue of diligence and interest in children;
- providing professional information means introducing children to information about the world of professions [3].

Of course, adult supervision and guidance is needed, and these processes are carried out directly by preschool educational institutions.

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